

An illustration at the top of the slide shows two hands, one from the left and one from the right, holding a heart. The heart is composed of four interlocking puzzle pieces: a blue piece on the top left, a red piece on the top right, a yellow piece on the bottom left, and a pink piece on the bottom right. The background is a light blue gradient with soft, curved lines.

AutSPACES

Platform Development Updates

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The
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autistica

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Updates

- New Contributions for the project.
- Continue working on the provided issues.
- Raised new PRs and getting reviewed.
- On the threshold of completing the Milestone 2.

Landing page

The image shows a landing page for AutSPACE. At the top, there are two small square icons. The main heading is 'AutSPACE'. Below it, a paragraph describes the platform's purpose. A 'How It Works' section contains a numbered list and three buttons: 'Sign Up', 'Sign In', and 'View Experiences'. A paragraph explains the goal of the platform. An 'Our Goals' section contains a numbered list. At the bottom, there is an email subscription form with a text input field, a 'Subscribe' button, and a 'powered by TinyLetter' link.

AutSPACE

AutSPACE is an online place where you can help make environments better for autistic people by sharing your stories about how your senses affect you.

How It Works

1. Sign up
2. Share a story about you
3. Choose who gets to view your story
4. Explore other people's stories

[Sign Up](#)

[Sign In](#)

[View Experiences](#)

Autistic people often have different sensory processing to people who are not autistic. By collecting together lots of autistic people's experiences, we can change spaces so that they are better for autistic people.

Our Goals

1. Research - increase understanding of sensory processing
2. Share strategies and experiences of autistic people
3. Advise organisations how to create better environments for autistic people

Enter your email address

We'll never share your email with anyone else.

[Subscribe](#)

powered by [TinyLetter](#)

Sign Up Page 2

[ABOUT](#)[Share](#)[View](#)[MyPage](#)[LOGIN](#)

Sign Up to AutSPACE

If you have another connection to autism, please write it here. For example sister, researcher or friend.

You can also leave this space blank.

- Friend of Autism person
- Parent of Autism person
- Sibling of Autism person
- Other Family member of Autistic person
- Healthcare/ Medical carer of Autistic person
- Autism researcher
- Educator for Autistic people
- Other

Please specify.

CONTINUE

View Experiences Page

[Home](#)[About](#)[View Experiences](#)[Login](#)

Explore

Here you can view the experiences and suggestions of other people

Autistic people often have different sensory processing to people who are not autistic. By collecting together lots of autistic people's experiences, we can change spaces so that they are better for autistic people.

DATE	PERSON'S AUTISM CONNECTION	
July 21	Researcher	Me and Timmy had some Ice Cream, and I decided to drop mine for the lolz. Timmy just watched me, mouth agape

Share Experiences Page

[Home](#) [View Experiences](#) [My Stories](#) [Share Experiences](#) [Logout](#)

Please share your experience

Write your experience here

Suggestions for what could have made your experience better

Write your suggestions here

You can choose who to share your experience with by selecting one or more of the options below:

- Share with the world by publishing on the AutSPACE website.
- Share, but only with people who have signed up and told us that they are autistic.
- Share for research
- Save as draft

Submit

Moderation Page

[Home](#)[About](#)[View Experiences](#)[Login](#)

Moderate

Here you can moderate experiences shared by other people.

DATE	PERSON'S AUTISM CONNECTION
July 21	Me and Timmy had some Ice Cream, and I decided to drop mine for the lolz. Timmy just watched me, mouth agape.
<input type="button" value="Approve"/>	<input type="button" value="Decline"/>

My Stories Page

AutSPACES

[Home](#)

[View Experiences](#)

[Home](#)

My Stories

Welcome to your personal AutSPACES page.

Here you can:

- * See the experiences you have saved and submitted.
- * Change sharing permissions for your experiences.

My Experiences

Upcoming Tasks

- Complete Milestone 2
- Start integrating the MVP pages together with the Open Humans
- Start working on Milestone 3
- Keep updating issues

Thanks

